

Effect of Good Behaviour Games on Classroom Incivilities among Junior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

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Abstract

This paper examined effect of good behaviour games on classroom incivilities among public junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. The study adopted the Quasi experimental one group research design. The population of the study comprised 26,162 JSS2 (2020/2021 section) students in 390 public Junior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. Sample size of 50 JSS2 students' intact class was used for the study through multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument for the study was Teachers' observation of classroom Adaptation Revised (TOCA-R) adapted by the researchers for the purpose of data collection with logical validity indices of 0.79. Cronbach alpha reliability method was used to test the internal consistence which yield 0.77. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. The finding showed that there is a significant effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivilities of public junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Based on the findings it was recommended among others that teachers strongly admonish to use this behavioural modification technique for conducive learning atmosphere during teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Good behaviour, Game, Classroom incivility.

Introduction

School is a spring of knowledge with planned programs for development of mind which will metamorphose into a good society. One of the factors that pose a threat to the achievement of schools' goals is classroom incivilities. Classroom incivilities are any negative, unruly, deviant, inappropriate, ill-manner of student to interrupt classroom activities. Segrist (2018) in Ani, Hendryadi and Ayoestina (2021) identified classroom

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incivilities as uncivil behaviours that often occur in the classroom to disrupt learning process (Ani et al., 2021) classroom incivility is any behaviour that impede the peaceful learning atmosphere. Thus, classroom incivilities are any ill manner, inappropriate act exhibit by student during teaching and learning process to disrupt the class. Thus classroom incivility has escalating cycle of actions and reactions, which can be distress to teaching and learning process. The full participation of students will be at the lowest ebb, according to Ball, & Carton ,Tindage and Anderson (2016), and Vuolo (2018) it leads to total detachment from the teaching and learning process. Thus, the attainment and accomplishment of classroom activities are at stake. Therefore, classroom incivilities constitute a challenge to both students and teachers during teaching and learning process.

Though teachers and students influence some of these behaviours and their responses. The choice to accept or disallow any behaviour pattern lies with teachers. Ya'u (2021) noted the occurring of incivility in classroom. The most common recent classroom incivilities of students during teaching and learning process among many include; Side conversations, Handsets, Pitching other students, out –of- seat behaviour and Napping. Classroom incivility does not occur in vacuum. Therefore, teachers should discourage whatsoever gestures, remarks that could threaten the involvement and cooperation of students during teaching and learning.

There are different styles and methods that teachers can employ to gain the student's full cooperation and undivided attention while teaching process is in progress, apart from rewards and punishment. One of such is good behaviour game.

Good behaviour game is a classroom based program to reduce disruptive behaviour. It was first used in 1969 by Barrish to reduce classroom disruptive behaviour of students. Rubow, Timothy & Joslyn (2018). It is an intervention strategy to curb aggressive and disruptive behaviour of student. According to Groves, May, Rees and Austin (2021) GBG is a classroom management intervention to elicit points towards a particular criterion. It is behaviour management scheme, an elaborate planned actions to encourage good behaviour and prevent disruptive behaviour of students while lesson is on. The game is based on a set of classroom-wide rules to inspire and boost good behaviour and discourage aggressive or disruptive behaviour in the classroom. It is teacher's planned strategy and not a curriculum, in which the teacher sets classroom's rules, to improve inappropriate classroom behaviour by rewarding the students' appropriate classroom behaviours.

The underlying aim of the game is that, as the students are group together, there is possibility of encouraging each other to comply with set rules to meet the behaviour expectation of the teacher. This interaction among peers do has a positive effect on every member of the team, so it tends to encourage pro social behaviour and academic engagement. Thus, improve internalization of norms and appropriate

behaviour (Coombes, Chan, Coombes, Chain, Allen & Foxcroft 2016). According to Kane, Allison, Reece, and Peterson (2015) the game do sustain mental health and well-being.

Once an undesirable behaviour is discouraged, a good one will be established immediately. This new appropriate behaviour continued for a long time in order for the student to properly learnt and embraced the new behaviour, which is known as maintenance. Coombes, Chan, Coombes, Chain, Allen & Foxcroft (2016) examined mixed –methods evaluation of Good Behaviour Game in English primary school. Six primary school comprises of 10 classrooms with a total of 222 children. The finding shown that pupils have developed a greater sense of social competency because they learned to correctly interpret different types of classroom communications which has positive effects on their sense of social competence, cooperative work (team). Rubow & Voumer & Joslyn (2018) carried out an investigation on the effect of Good Behaviour on students of Alternative learning centre (ALC) for children with records of severe behavioural problems. Two intact classrooms were used. It was found out that good behaviour game is effective for reducing disruptive classroom behaviour with students who have emotional disorder. It is for this reason that this study seeks to examine the effect of good behaviour games on classroom incivilities among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State?
2. What is the difference in pre-test and post-test scores of students Subjected to good behaviour game and those not subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses would be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State?

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in pre-test and post-test scores of students Subjected to good behaviour game and those not subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State?

Research method

Quasi experimental one- group pretest- posttest research design was adopted for the study. This is because the classroom incivility is inherent in these students (preexisting).The population of the study comprised 26,162 JSS2 (2020/2021 section) students in 390 public Junior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State. Multi stage Random sampling technique was used to select the sample. Sample size of 50 student intact class (entire class members) was used for the study. The instrument adapted to collect data for the study was “Teachers’ observation of classroom Adaptation Revised” (TOCA-R). The (TOCA-R) scale are of 20 items to measure student social adaptation and behaviour in the class. The instrument was divided into three sections, items was on emotional regulation, social competence, pro-social behaviour, Authority acceptance, attention, concentration, Academic readiness, social isolation and teacher-student behaviour. The instrument was validated by experts with logical validity index of 0.79. Cronbach alpha method was used to test internal consistency which reliability index yield 0.77. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t test.

Gaming Rules

The game is based on a set of classroom-wide rules:

The following four classroom rules and expectations were used for the experiment:

1. Students must pay attention to the lesson.
2. No student must interrupt classroom activity.
3. Out of seat without permission attracts penalty, and
4. Yelling or noise from any students during class activity to interrupt is forbidding.

These rules are to inspire and boost good behavior and discourage aggressive or disruptive behaviour in the classroom. The game was played in the class for a period of 20 minutes to 45 minutes. The game was geared towards the curriculum like reading, and writing. There was no additional requirement on curriculum time.

The programme is in three distinct stages which involves interaction between teachers and the students.

Phase 1

The teacher gives definite classroom expectation to the entire class, with major emphasis on social and the academic expectation within classroom setting, during teaching and learning process. The teacher and the students are conversant with the rules and expectation as they play the game intermittently. Any of the

team can win by completing the game with no or little rules transgression. The winning team is therefore reinforced by given verbal and tangible rewards at the end of the game.

Phase 2

The teacher takes the game beyond the classroom setting. Student are to observe the rules and expectations of the game, even outside the classroom. Teacher emphasis is on the behaviour he or she wants to stamp out and the behaviour he or she wants to stamp into the mind of the students. Students will be monitor unknowing.

Phase 3

Teacher will not give prior warning or signal to the students. They are constantly monitor to ensure they comply with the set rules and expectation of the game, even outside the context of the game. And through all classroom activities and outside the classroom (kane et al 2015).

Introduction process of GBG into a classroom setting is a relatively simple. It requires five steps to put the game in practice.

Procedure for Data Collection

Quasi experimental research design was used. JSS 2A Intact (whole class members) class of ECWA junior secondary school was used. During the period, the researcher met with the English subject teacher of JSS 2A class used for the experiment and discuss the suitability of various reinforcement for appropriate behaviour in the classroom. It was decided and agreed that stationary (exercise books and biro) should be used. The class was divided into two team based on the side of the classroom seating arrangement (left or right side) balance for gender, behaviour and ability.

The researcher occupied a position in the classroom, as classroom assistance to the teacher where all the students were clearly seen. There was initial observation (pretest) before data collection in which the classroom assistant (the researcher) took record of frequency of talking and out of seat behaviour on a tally chart during each 40 minutes of the lesson periods.

TOCA-R was completed by the teacher for each of students in the class, prior three weeks to the intervention on core activities in the classroom to determine a baseline for each child and also at the end of the intervention.

Weekly over the implementation period, the teacher and researcher took record of number of rule infractions incurred over a predetermined time period (typically 15-40mins) during which GBG was played.

The rules of the game were explained by the teacher to the teams before the commencement. The two major rules to this game were on the two target behaviour which are;

1. Talking without permission from the teacher. That means no audible sound from the mouth. No dragging of feet. No yawning like wild animal. Whenever help is needed with your work, you signal to the teacher (raise your hand) and do not shout 'Ma', and the teacher would come to give the help as soon as possible.
2. Out of seat without permission from the teacher. No movement from your seat to another, if the need arises, you raise your hand to seek for permission from the teacher.

A poster stating the two rules of the game was placed on the wall in front of the classroom when the game was play and not at any other time. This means the poster was hung on the wall at the beginning of the GBG and every subsequent period in which the game was played.

As the game commenced, the researcher (classroom Assistant) took records of the frequencies of the two disruptive behaviour (talking and out of seat behaviour). Disruption was scored whenever any of the student from any of the group.

1. Call out without teacher's permission.
2. Drag his or her leg while the lesson is on
3. Leave seat without permission, this is whenever any student's buttocks and knees are not in contact with his or her seat for like 3minutes.
4. Polite to others in our expression and attitudes.

Also, a disruption was scored whenever any of the student engaged himself or herself in any behaviour unrelated to the returning to his or her seat for 3 minutes after he or she completes the task obtain permission for. Frequency records of talking and out-of-seat behaviour was recorded on a tally chart during each 45 minutes session. Higher score shows high frequency in talking and out of seat during lesson. Data was collected in two sessions in a week for six weeks. In contrast, probe data comprises similar information was collected during a different part of the school day while the GBG was not be played. The purpose of conducting a probe was to determine the level of behavioural generalization that the students have been able to acquire and for teachers to observe their students' behaviour and learning abilities when there was no direct knowledge or confirmation of an impending reward for good behaviour.

For the first session of the game, there was predetermined numbers of demerits which was used as a yard stick to determine the losing team. The researcher (classroom assistant) explained to the teams that they have to score below the limit to earn a reward and win the game. The researcher explained to the teams that if single student sabotage (only him or her having 5 – 10 demerits strikes than any other students in the team) he or she would be removed from the team and be place on an independent team. And the

demerit limit for both the individual student and the team was calculated based on the overall class limit and the limit for the team. This done to adjust accordingly, and guide against been bias.

During the game, the researcher (class assistant) responds to rule violation by marking strike on the board in front of the team that violated the rule as feedback. This continued till the time for the games over and a team lost out of the game. When a team or saboteur reach the demerit limit, the researcher no longer provide demerit for the particular team.

After the first session of GBG, the researcher began the other session by reviewing the rules. Then, she announced the two teams. Also, the student who engaged more in the disruptive behaviour was evenly distributed across the teams to make both teams equally likely to win. She also announced the rewards they could receive. She explained how many demerits a team could be given before losing out of the game. The essence of the game is to stamp out the disruptive behaviour such as aggression, hyperactive or impulsive behaviour, screaming, excessive or persistent noise, as well as confrontation with teachers and students, which are common anti- social behaviours among students. And to stamp in emotional stability, social competence, authority acceptance, academic readiness and pro-social behaviour (which include team work, rendering helping to other students in need without demanding for compensation in return).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation Mean Scores Showing Effect of Good Behavior Game on Classroom Incivility among Junior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Groups	Pre-test		Std Dev	Post-test	
	N	Mean		Mean	Std Dev
Experimental Group (Good Behaviour)	30	44.17	3.41	56.10	7.45
Control Group (Without Good Behavior)	30	35.30	1.92	37.67	3.87

Table1 shows results on the effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Results indicated that the pre-test mean and standard deviation scores for the experimental group were given as 44.17 and 3.41 respectively while the post-test mean and standard

deviation score were given as 56.10 and 7.45 respectively. As for the control group, the pre-test mean and standard deviation scores given as 35.30 and 1.92 while the post-test mean and standard deviation scores are given as 37.67 and 3.87. It is however observed mean scores of students in the experimental group was higher than the mean scores of those in the control group. This therefore shows that good behaviour game had a higher effect on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Showing Difference in the Pre-test and Post test scores of Students Subjected to Good Behaviour Game and those not subjected to Good Behaviour Game on Classroom Incivility among Junior Secondary School Students in Nasarawa

Groups	Pre-test		Std Dev	Post-test		Std Dev
	N	Mean		Mean	Achievement Gain	
Experimental Group (Good Behaviour Game)	30	44.17	3.14	56.10	7.45	11.93
Control Group (Without Good Behaviour)	30	35.30	1.92	37.67	3.87	2.37

Table 2 shows results on the difference in the pre-test and post-test of students subjected to good behaviour game and those not subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa. Results indicated that the mean achievement gain for the experimental group was given as 11.93 (good behaviour) while the mean achievement gains of the control group (without fear appeal) was given as 2.37. This therefore shows that pre-test and post-test scores of students subjected to good behaviour game was higher than those not subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1 was tested using analysis of co-variance as shown in table 3

Table 3. T-Test Statistics showing Effect of Good Behaviour Game on classroom activities among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Experimental Group	30	56.10	7.45	29	8.434	0.000	Reject H0 ₁	Significant
Control Group	30	37.67	3.87					

Table 3 indicates the significance of effect of good behaviour game on classroom activities among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Results showed that the calculated value of t is given as 8.434. P-value of group at degree of freedom of 29 is given as $P = 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the P-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis 1 is therefore rejected. Thus, there is a significant effect of good behaviour game on classroom activities among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State.

Hypothesis 2 was tested using analysis of co-variance as shown in table: 4 below

Table 4. T-Test Statistics showing Difference Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Students Subjected to Good Behaviour Game on classroom activities

Variables	N	Mean Gains	Std Dev	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Experimental Group	30	11.93	4.31	29	5.436	0.000	Reject H0 ₂	Significant
Control Group	30	2.37	1.85					

Table 4. indicates the significance of difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of students subjected to fear good behaviour game on classroom activities and those not subjected to good behaviour game among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa. Results showed that the calculated value of t is given as 5.436. The P-value is given as $P = 0.000 < 0.05$, since the P-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis 2 is therefore rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of students

subjected to good behaviour game on classroom activities and those not subjected to good behaviour among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State.

Discussion

Findings on hypothesis 1 showed that there is a significant effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. This finding is in agreement with those of Coombes, Chain, Allen and Foxcroft (2016) which indicated that the use of good behaviour behaviour had significant effect on classroom learning.

Findings on hypothesis 2 showed that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of students subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility and those not subjected to fear appeal among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. This finding is similar of Rubow, Voumer and Joslyn (2018) showed that good behaviour game has significant effect on students' alternative learning for children with records of severe behavioural problems to the which showed that the use of good behaviour game has helped in correcting the disruptive behaviour of learners in school.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is a significant effect of good behaviour game on classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Results further reveal that there is a significant difference in pre-test and post-test mean scores of students subjected to good behaviour game on classroom incivility and those not subjected to good appeal among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Based on these results. it was therefore recommended among others that the use of good behaviour game be encouraged in order to promote healthy classroom incivility among junior secondary school students in Nasarawa State. Additionally, workshops and seminars should be organized to train school counsellors and teachers on how to effectively employ the use of good behaviour game in classroom incivility.

References

- Ani, C., Hendryadi, H. and Ayoestina M. (2021) 'Work place and classroom incivility and learning engagement: The moderating Role of locus of control' published: 18 feb., 202 *International journal for Educational Integrity*. Article number:4 (2021).
- Ball H, Carton, S. T., Tindage M. F and Anderson A.O (2016) Student civility in the college classroom; Exploring student use and effects of classroom citizenship behaviour. *Commun Edu* 65(1):64-82 <https://doi-org/10-1080/03634523-2015-1061197> Article Google Scholar.
- Coombes, L., Chan, G., Allen, D. and Foxcroft D. (2016). Mixed-Methods Evaluation of the Good Behaviour

Game in English Primary Schools

Groves, E., Richard, J M., Rees, R. E, and Austin, J. L (2021) Adapting the good behaviour game theories for special Education classrooms.2021. *Psychology in the schools*59(5) <https://www.researchgate.net> 3493

Kane, E. Allison, H., Reece L. and Peterson, (2015) University of Nebraska- Lincoln. *Good behaviour Game program Brief*, Dec., 2015s

Rubow, C. Timothy R. V and P., Joslyn, R (2018)'Effect of the Good Behaviour Game on Student and Teacher's Behaviour in an Alternative School *Journal of Applied Behaviour Analysis* 2018 51, 382-39 <https://www.researchgate.net> 3241

Segrist D. Bartels LK; Nordstrom CR (2018) "but everyone else is doing it" a social norms perspective on classroom incivility. *Coll Teach* 66(4):181-186. <https://doi.org/co./080/87567555.2018-1482858>, article on *google scholar*.

Vuolo J (2018) Student nurse experiences of incivility and the impact on learning and emotional wellbeing in: *Journal of nursing education and practice* <https://uhra-herts.ac-uk/handle/2299/20652> Google scholar Retrieved on 12th may, 2022

Ya'u, A. S., Kabiru, M. U. and Danlami, H. (2021) Effectiveness of fear Appeals and Good Behaviour Games on Classroom Incivility among Primary School Pupils in Ungogo Local Government Kano.

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